

1 **Immune receptors participate in germ layer lineage choice of pluripotent stem cells to the**
2 **endoderm.**

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7 The organ systems of the human body are each derived from three germ layers: the endoderm,
8 mesoderm, and ectoderm. We defined here using transcriptomics a minimal set of components required or
9 important for germ layer fate choice to the endoderm in the first trimester of human development. We
10 describe a requirement for Epsti1 in germ layer, accompanied by silencing of Ano1 and Lingo1 during
11 lineage choice from pluripotent stem cells in *Homo sapiens*.

12 Citations

13 1. Mi, S., Miller, R.H., Lee, X., Scott, M.L., Shulag-Morskaya, S., Shao, Z., Chang, J., Thill, G.,
14 Levesque, M., Zhang, M. and Hession, C., 2005. LINGO-1 negatively regulates myelination by
15 oligodendrocytes. Nature neuroscience, 8(6), pp.745-751.